

METACOGNITIVE AND COGNITIVE STRATEGIES

Mirzaeva Iroda Javlon qizi

TTPU, EFL teacher

daffodilme@mail.ru

Strategy is one of the most effective ways of improving academic performance for children with learning difficulties. This way will show you how to do it, will provide a forum to discuss your experiences and questions. It includes metacognitive and cognitive strategies.

Metacognitive strategy is a critically important, overlooked component of learning. It involves planning, goal-setting and monitoring one's progress. All of these activities are metacognitive in nature. By teaching students these skills all of which can be learned, we can improve student learning. There are three critical steps to teaching metacognition.

1. Teaching students that their ability to learn is mutable.
2. Teaching planning and goal setting.
3. Giving students ample opportunities to practice monitoring their learning and adapting as necessary.

Metacognition, in a broad sense, means “Big thinking.” That is, it implies thinking about thinking. Teachers work with students so they become more strategic thinkers by helping them understand the way they are processing the information. Questioning, visualizing and synthesizing information are all ways that readers can examine their thinking process. By practicing and applying metacognitive strategy, students will become good readers, capable of handling any text across curriculum.

Cognitive strategy is one type of learning strategy that learners use in order to learn more successfully. These include repetition, organizing new language, summarizing meaning, guessing meaning from context, using imagery for memorization. Cognitive strategy is one of the most effective strategies for learning

language. That is because every learner remembers new words by visualizing them, represented in a memorable situation. This makes it easier and faster to recall these words. Activities which can be described as cognitive strategies include making mind maps, visualization, mnemonics, using key words in reading comprehension, underlining key words and scanning. Cognitive strategies are useful tools in assisting with learning problems. They provide a structure for learning when a task cannot be completed through a series of steps. A cognitive strategy serves to support the learner as he or she develops internal procedures that enable him or her to perform tasks that are complex. Cognitive strategies are important in order to comprehend reading. In other words, it can help students understand what they read. The usage of cognitive strategies can increase the efficiency with which the learner approaches a learning task.

It should be noted that metacognitive and cognitive strategies are important for learners. Although most individuals of normal intelligence engage in metacognitive regulation rule, some are more metacognitive than others, and their metacognitive abilities tend to be more successful in the cognitive exertion. Metacognitive and cognitive strategies are closely intertwined and dependent upon each other. The study of metacognition has provided educational psychologists with insight about the cognitive processes involved in learning and showed how different successful students were from their less successful peers. It also holds several implications for instructional interventions, such as teaching students how to be more aware of their learning process and products as well as how to regulate those processes for more effective learning. Both of them are very important for language learning. In metacognitive strategies, learners do all tasks regardless of their tendency to analyze themselves or not. Metacognition is a three-part process. To be successful thinkers, students must:

1. Develop a plan before reading.
2. Monitor their understanding of text.
3. Evaluate their thinking after reading.

It is worth mentioning that learners are taught new tasks with visual aids by teachers. They can understand more with visualizing and they should practice their

comprehension skills. Practice will increase the ability to use information and skills in new situation. Metacognitive and cognitive strategies help students become reflective and critical thinkers and show students how to be better learners.

References

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